

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING KETOPROFEN TABLET BY USING DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD

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INTRODUCTION

Tablets are solid dosage form which is the conventional as well as have many advantages over other dosage forms. Tablets are the most popular dosage form; about 70% of the total medicines are dispensed in the form of tablet. Tablets had different shapes, sizes, as well as weight depending on medicinal substances and the intended mode of administration. In this paper the some advantages as well as some disadvantages of tablets, the basic ingredients that are commonly found in tablets.^[1]

➤ Definition

According to the Indian Pharmacopoeia Pharmaceutical tablets are solid, flat or biconvex dishes, unit dosage form, prepared by compressing a drugs or a mixture of drugs, with or without diluents. Tablet is defined as a compressed solid dosage form containing medicaments with or without excipients. They vary in shape and differ greatly in size and weight, depending on

amount of medicinal substances and the intended mode of administration of tablet preparation.^[2]

➤ **Properties**^[2]

1. Should be elegant product having its own identity while being free of defects such as chips, cracks, discoloration and contamination.
2. Should have strength to withstand the rigors of shocks encountered in its production, packaging, shipping and dispensing.
3. Should have the physical stability to maintain its physical attributes over time.
4. Must be able to release the medicament agent(s) in the body in a predictable and reproducible manner.
5. Must have a suitable chemical stability over time so as not to allow alteration of the medicinal agent(s). Various types of the tablets are briefly reviewed.

➤ **Advantages**^[3]

- 1) Tablets are unit dosage forms and offer the greatest capabilities of all oral dosage forms for the greatest dose precision and the least content variability.
- 2) They are easiest and cheapest to package and strip.
- 3) Low in cost.
- 4) Lighter and compact.
- 5) Having greatest chemical and microbial stability over all oral dosage forms.
- 6) Suitable for large scale production.
- 7) Easy to swallow with least tendency for hang-up.
- 8) Objectionable odor and bitter taste can be masked by coating technique.
- 9) Sustained release product is possible by enteric coating.

➤ **Disadvantages**^[3]

- 1) Difficult to swallow in case of children and unconscious patients.
- 2) Some drugs resist compression into dense compacts, owing to amorphous nature, low density character.
- 3) Drugs with poor wetting, slow dissolution properties, optimum absorption high in GIT may be difficult to formulate or manufacture as a tablet that will still provide adequate or full drug bioavailability.
- 4) Bitter tasting drugs, drugs with an objectionable odor or drugs that are sensitive to oxygen may require encapsulation or coating. In such cases, capsule may offer the best and lowest cost.
- 5) Irritant effects on the GI mucosa by some solids (e.g., Ketoprofen).

6) Possibility of bioavailability problems resulting from slow disintegration and dissolution.

➤ **Ingredients**^[2]

Table no. 1.1 Ingredient.

Sr no.	Ingredient	Example
1	Diluents	Lactose, Sorbitol, Mannitol, Xylitol
2	Binders	Sucrose, Gelatin, Starch.
3	Lubricant	Calcium Sterate, Glyceryl Palmitostearate, Magnesium
4	Glidants	Magnesium Trisilicate, Cellulose, Starch, Talc, Tribasic Calcium Phosphate
5	Anti-adherents	Corn Starch, Metallic Sterate, Talc
6	Disintegrant	Alginic acid, Carboxy methyl cellulose, Cellulose, Colloidal Silicon Dioxide, Croscarmellos Sodium, Crospovidone, Potassium Polacrilin, Povidone
7	Coloring agents	FD&C or D&C Dyes or Lake Pigments
8	Flavoring agent	Ethyl Maltol; Ethyl Vanillin, Menthol, Vanillin
9	Absorbent	Kaolin, Magnesium Aluminum Silicate, Tricalcium Phosphate

- 1) **Diluents:** Diluents are fillers used to make required bulk of the tablet when the drug dosage itself is inadequate to produce the bulk. Also used to improve cohesion, to permit use of direct compression.
- 2) **Binders:** To form cohesive compacts for directly compressed tablet.
- 3) **Lubricants:** Lubricants are intended to prevent adhesion of the tablet materials to the surface of dies and punches, reduce inter particle friction and may improve the rate of flow of the tablet granulation.
- 4) **Glidant's:** Glidants are intended to promote flow of granules or powder material by reducing the friction between the particles.
- 5) **Anti-adherents:** Anti-adherents are added to the tablet formulations to prevent the material from sticking to the walls of the tablet press.
- 6) **Disintegrates:** Added to a tablet formulation to facilitate its breaking or disintegration when it contact in water in the GIT.
- 7) **Coloring Agents:** The use of colors and dyes in a tablet has three purposes: (A) Masking of off color drugs (B) Product Identification (C) Production of more elegant product.
- 8) **Flavouring Agents:** Flavoring oils are needed for chewable tablets. The oil is generally added in a dry form such as spray-dried beads.
- 9) **Absorbents:** The inclusion of substance with a high affinity to water. Hygroscopic materials, if present, render the blend wet and difficult to handle during manufacture.

➤ **Types of tablet^[4]**

1. Orally ingested Tablet
2. Compressed Tablet
3. Multiple Compressed
4. Chewable Tablet
5. Sugar Coated Tablet
6. Film Coated Tablet
7. Enteric Coated Tablet

➤ **Methods of preparation^[4]**

Granulation method can be broadly classified into two types: Wet granulation and Dry granulation.

1. Wet Granulation

Fig. no. 1.1: Wet Granulation.

The most widely used process of agglomeration in pharmaceutical industry is wet granulation. Wet granulation process simply involves wet massing of the powder blend with a granulating liquid, wet sizing and drying.

Important steps involved in the wet granulation

- i. Mixing of the drug(s) and excipients.
- ii. Preparation of binder solution.

- iii. Mixing of binder solution with powder mixture to form wet mass.
- iv. Drying of moist granules.
- v. Mixing of screened granules with disintegrant, glidant, and lubricant.

2. Dry Granulation

In dry granulation process the powder mixture is compressed without the use of heat and solvent. It is the least desirable of all methods of granulation. The two basic procedures are to form a compact of material by compression and then to mill the compact to obtain a granules. Two methods are used for dry granulation. The more widely used method is slugging, where the powder is recompressed and the resulting tablet or slug are milled to yield the granules. The other method is to recompress the powder with pressure rolls using a machine such as Chilosonator.

Fig. no.1.2 Dry Granulation.

3. Direct Compression

Direct compression is the simplest and most economical method for the manufacturing of the tablet because it requires less processing step than other technique.

INTRODUCTION OF KETOPROFEN

➤ HISTORY OF KETOPROFEN

Ketoprofen (Orudis), a highly potent and safe non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug of the

propionic acid derivative group, was synthesized in France by Rhône-Poulenc chemists in 1967, 3 years after the prototype ibuprofen. Ketoprofen was introduced in 1973 in France and the United Kingdom for anti-inflammatory use. It was patented in 1967 and approved for medical use in 1980. Ketoprofen is non steroidal anti inflammatory drug (NSAID) It is used for treat pain, inflammation, Swelling stiffness and joint pain. It is available only with doctor's prescription. "Ketoprofen in relieving moderate sever pain & improving functional stands and general condition was significantly better than that of ibuprofen & diclofenac."^[16]

FORMULA – C₁₆H₁₄O₃

STRUCTURE

MECHANISM OF ACTION

Ketoprofen inhibits COX-2 enzyme which results in decrease in production of prostaglandins which is responsible for conveying of pain and inflammation signals in the body.

It also inhibits COX-1 enzyme which is responsible for the side effects of drug like GI ulcerations. Ketoprofen also have anti-bradykinin activity and lysosomal membrane-stabilization action. Drug also action the hypothalamus and produces antipyretic effects which results in increased peripheral blood flow, vasodilatation and heat dissipation.^[14]

STRUCTUREACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP

SAR of ketoprofen canbe summarized as follows

Activity decreases on placing the phenoxy group in the ortho or Para position of the arylpropionic acid. Replacing carbonyl group between two aromatic rigs with Oxygen Bridge produces another marketed analogue known as fenoprofen.^[9]

SIDE EFFECT^[13]**Side effect of ketoprofen are**

- Allergic reactions
- Skin reactions
- Shortness of breath
- Weight gain
- Vision changes
- Indigestion
- Nausea
- Jaundice
- Pale skin
- Constipation
- Headache
- Tiredness
- Ringing in the ear
- Insomnia

MARKETED PRODUCTS^[19]**1. Brand name:** ketophen

Manufacturer: Pharma Corp Inc

Type: Tablet

Unit : 50mg

2. Brand name: ketophen(100mg)

Manufacturer: Pharma Corp Inc

Type: Tablet

Unit: 100mg

3. Brand name: ketopatch

Manufacturer: Emcure Pharmaceuticals Limited

Type: Transdermal patch

Unit: 30mg

4. Brand name: Ketoplast plaster

Manufacturer: Zubenteves Healthcares

Type: Transdermal Patch

Unit: 20mg

5. Brand name: Ostofen

Manufacturer: Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd.

Type: Tablet

Unit: 50mg

6. Brand name: Redufen

Manufacturer: Unique Life Sciences(P) Ltd.

Type: Tablet

Unit: 50mg

USES OF KETOPROFEN^[19]

- To Relieve Minor Aches And Pain From Headaches,
- Menstrual Periods
- Toothaches
- The Common Cold
- Muscle Aches
- Backaches
- Reduce Fever

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mahesh Dattatray Dokhe, et.al (2020): In the past some years the number of products based on new drug delivery system has significantly increased, and this extension is expected to continue in the future. Tablet dosage form is convenient and relevant as compared to other dosage forms. Innovation in tablet dosage form provide product of higher selectivity for the drug for medical treatment. There are so many existing drug delivery technologies in recent years developed. This is an attempt to being made to compile some of the most successfully marketed drug delivery technology in this article. The present review focus on innovation in tablet system i.e. Tablet in tablet system. Evolution of an existing drug molecule from a conventional form in to said technology can improve performance in terms of safety, efficacy and patient compliance.^[03]

Antonio Buzharevski, et.al(2019): Ketoprofen is a widely used non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that also exhibits cytotoxic activity against various cancers. This makes ketoprofen an attractive structural lead for the development of new NSAIDs and cytotoxic agents. Recently, the incorporation of carboranes as phenyl mimetic in structures of established drugs has emerged as an attractive strategy in drug design. Herein, we report the synthesis and evaluation of four novel carborane-containing derivatives of ketoprofen, two of which are prodrug esters with a nitric oxide-releasing moiety. One of these prodrug esters exhibited high cytostatic activity against melanoma and colon cancer cell lines. The most pronounced activity was found in cell lines that are sensitive to oxidative stress, which was apparently induced by the ketoprofen analogue.^[17]

Abdalwali A. Saif, et al (2018): Pharmaceutical manufacturing has largely grown in recent years. This and many other factors have led to the ability of manipulating pharmaceutical dosage forms and routes of administration. One example of such unique dosage forms is Fast Dissolving Tablets (FDTs), which are solid dosage forms intended to be dissolved in mouth in a relatively short time, ranging from a few seconds to up to 3 minutes. In this research, ketoprofen was chosen to be the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in a fast dissolving tablets formulation, being a model of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). Ketoprofen is widely used as an analgesic, and being so, the faster the effect, the better the dosage form. Therefore solid preparation of Ketoprofen with super disintegrants like Croscarmellose sodium, and/or Crospovidone in different ratios were prepared with a view to increase its effect by decreasing the time required for the drug to be released. The ingredients of the formulation were tested for incompatibilities by using IR method; all ingredients were compatible. Ketoprofen and the excipients were mixed together and submitted to pre-formulation tests. The powders were then compressed into tablets by direct compression method. The prepared batches of tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, disintegration time, wetting time and in-vitro drug release which tested in comparing with Profenid®. Ketoprofen FDTs prepared showed better results than Profenid® depending on dissolution test.

Saddam J. Nasser, et.al (2012): Ketoprofen is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory (NSAID) drug with analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic effects. It is widely used in the treatment of inflammation and pain associated with rheumatic disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and in soft tissue injury. The purpose of this study was to prepare an

oral disintegrating tablets of ketoprofen by simple method. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method and different ratios of various subliming agents or super disintegrants were incorporated. Then these tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, weight variation, water absorption ratio, disintegrating time and dissolution time.^[10]

Kwabena of ori-Kwakye, et.al (2010): The aim of this study was to formulate and evaluate the physical properties of two tablet formulations of metformin and paracetamol intended for fast disintegration and release in the gastrointestinal tract. The tablet formulations were prepared using similar excipients and manufacturing procedure in a local manufacturing site in Ghana over a ten (10) month period. The moisture content, angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, hausner ratio, and Carr's index of granulates of the two formulations prepared by wet granulation was determined. The physical properties of the compressed tablets, namely; uniformity of weight, drug content, friability, disintegration time, crushing strength, tensile strength and dissolution were assessed. The tablet quality index of the formulations was evaluated using the crushing strength-friability/disintegration time (CSFR/DT) ratio. Granulates of both tablet formulations had good flow properties. The paracetamol tablets had lower crushing strength and disintegration time ($p < 0.05$) than metformin tablets. However, paracetamol tablets possessed higher friability and tensile strength ($p < 0.05$) than metformin tablets.^[12]

Tejas wi Santosh Ubhe, et. Al(2010): Medicines are not only a science; it is also an art. It does not consist of compounding pills and plasters; it deals with the very processes of life, which must be understood before they may be guided. Pharmaceutical oral solid dosage forms have been used widely for decades mainly due to their convenience of administration and their suitability for delivery for delivery of drugs for systemic effects. The tablets can be made directly from powders or from granules pellets, or from film-coated multiple units. Tablets are now the most popular dosage form, accounting for some 70% of all ethical pharmaceutical preparations produced. Tablets may be defined as solid pharmaceutical dosage forms containing drug substances with or without suitable diluents and prepared by either compression or moulding methods. Hence, tablets can be broadly classified as compressed tablets and moulded tablets.^[02]

Dali Shukla, et.al(2008): Mouth dissolving tablets are well established dosage forms available in the market. The numerous advantages that they offer to the patients in terms of compliance as well as to the manufacturers in terms of huge revenues by line extension of

products are well known. In spite of such popularity, there seems to be lack of a standardized system to characterize these dosage forms. Enormous work has been done in this field, wherein some of the researchers have developed their own methods of evaluation. This article attempts to present a detailed review regarding technological advances made so far in the area of evaluation of mouth dissolving tablets with respect to special characteristics of these unique dosage forms. In the absence of any available standardized method, the author's recommendation on critical issues in the field may be considered.^[15]

Hubert G Leufkens, et.al(1992): Study objective-The aim was to determine if a new controlled release formulation (Oscorel) of the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) ketoprofen has been preferentially prescribed in patients with prior history of gastrointestinal disturbances. Design-The study was a pharmacy records based comparison of the rates of prior prescribing of drugs indicated for peptic ulcer treatment in first recipients of Oscorel in 1989 versus recipients of other NSAID products. Setting-A representative panel of Dutch community pharmacies serving approximately 425 000 people was used.^[16]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Aim:- Formulation and evaluation of Fast dissolving ketoprofen tablet by using direct compression method.

Objective

1. To formulate fast dissolving direct compressed tablet.
2. To evaluate fast dissolving direct compressed tablet.

PLAN OF WORK

Plan of work for formulation and evaluation of ketoprofen tablet includes following steps:-

1. Literature survey
2. Procurement of drug and excipients
3. Pre formulation study
 - a) Identification of drug
 - b) Melting point
 - c) solubility of drug
 - d) standard calibration curve
4. Formulation of the tablet
 - a) Method - direct compression method

- b) Material- API and excipients
- 5. λ max
- 6. Characterisation of tablets
 - a) Physical appearance
 - b) UV-Spectroscopy
 - c) Hardness
 - d) Thickness
 - e) Friability
 - f) Weight variation
 - g) Disintegration test
 - h) Dissolution test

DRUG & EXCIPIENTS

1] Ketoprofen

Fig No. 5.1: Structure of Ketoprofen.^[19]

Table No. 5.1: Drug Profile (Ketoprofen).^[19]

Molecular Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃
Molecular weight	254.28 g/mol
IUPAC Name	2(3-Benzoylphenyl) propionic acid
Brand name	Ordis and Oruvail
Synonyms	Capisten dexketoprofen
Solubility	Alcohol, (DMF) Dimethyl formamide
Melting point	91-96 ^o C
Category	NSAID Analgesic Anti-pyretic
Use	To treat pain, inflammation, swelling, stiffness and joint pain
MOA	It acts by inhibition of COX-2 and enzyme involved in prostaglandin synthesis via the arachidonic acid pathway. This results in decreased level of prostaglandin that mediates pain, fever, inflammation
Route of administration	Oral and intravenous
Route of elimination	In a 24 hr period approximately 80% of an administered dose

	ofketoprofen is excreted in the urine , primarily as the glucouconide metabolite
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2) Crospovidone

Figure no. 5.2: Structure of crospovidone.^[19]

Table no. 5.2 excipient profile(crospovidone)^[19]

Molecular formula	(C ₆ H ₉ N ₀) _n
Molecular weight	111.14
IUPAC name	1-ethenyl pyrrolidin-2-one
Solubility	Insoluble in water,ethanoland ether
Use	Food additives filter aid, stabilizer

3] Mannitol

Figure no. 5.3: Structure of mannitol.^[19]

Table no. 5.3 excipient profile(mannitol).^[19]

Molecular formula	C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₆
Molecular weight	182.172g/mol
IUPAC name	Hexane - 1,2,3,4,5,6-Hexol
Solubility	Soluble in water, alcoholpyridine and glycerol
Uses	1. Reduce of intracranialpressure and brainmass 2. Reduce intraocular pressure

4] Sorbitol

Figure no. 5.4 structure of sorbitol.^[19]

Table no.5.4 excipient profile(sorbitol).^[19]

Molecular Formula	C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₆
Molecular Weight	182.17 g/mol
IUPAC Name	(2S,3R,4R,5R)-Hexane-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexol
Solubility	highly soluble in water
Melting Point	95 °C
Category	It falls into a category of sugar alcohols called polyols.
Uses	used as a laxative to relieve constipation, and also as a urologic irrigating fluid
Description	Sorbitol is a sugar alcohol found in fruits and plants with diuretic, laxative and cathartic property.

5] Magnesium stearate

Figure no. 5.5: Structure of magnesium stearate.^[19]Table no. 5.5 Excipient Profile(Mg stearate)^[19]

Molecular formula	Mg(C ₁₈ H ₃₅ O ₂) ₂
Molecular weight	591.244
IUPAC Name	Magnesium octadecanoate
Solubility	Slightly soluble in benzene
Melting point	88.5°C
Category	Lubricants
Description	It is magnesium salt of fatty, stearic acid
Uses	Binder Thickeners Emulsifier

6] Colloidal Silicon Dioxide (s)

Figure no. 5.6: Structure of colloidal S.^[19]

Table no. 5.6 excipient profile(colloidal S).^[19]

Molecular formula	SiO ₂
Molecular weight	60.1
IUPAC name	Silicon dioxide
Solubility	Dissolve in hot solution of alkali hydroxide
Melting point	1710°C
Category	Oxide of silica
Description	It is fumed silica, prepared by vapour phase hydrolysis of silicon compound
Uses	Anti-caking agent, Adsorbants, Disintegrant

7] Microcrystalline Cellulose

Figure no. 5.7: Structure of microcrystalline cellulose.^[19]Table no. 5.7 excipient profile(microcrystalline cellulose)^[19]

Molecular formula	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₁₁
Molecular weight	370.35
IUPAC Name	4-O-[(15)-hexopyranosyl]-D-glycero-hexopyranose
Solubility	Insoluble in water
Melting point	250°C
Description	MCC is purified partially depolymerized cellulose prepared by treating alpha-cellulose, obtained as pulp from fibrous plant material
Category	Glycoside
Uses	Texturizer Emulsifier Bulking agent

METHODS AND MATERIAL

METHODS

Direct compression Method

Direct compression is the simplest and most economical method for the manufacturing of the tablet because it requires less processing step than other technique. direct compression is the

most straight forward manufacturing option, with the fewest steps, making it the easiest to control and least expensive. The direct compression tablet process uses two primary process steps: blending the API with excipients and compressing the finished tablets. Apart from process simplicity, the key advantages of direct compression vs wet granulation include reduced capital, labor and energy costs for manufacturing, and the avoidance of water for granulation for water sensitive drug substance. Despite involving only a few steps, product design in the direct compression method for tablets can be challenging because of the numerous competing objectives. Among several requirements, the compression mix has to flow to ensure a consistent tablet weight; it has to compress and compact into robust tablets; and the resulting tablets have to remain stable over time to maintain safety and efficacy. As evidenced, there are advantages and disadvantages of direct compression method because it's directly impacted by material properties by material properties since these are not altered by granulation process steps. Therefore, it requires increased performance, quality and consistency from starting ingredients, including excipients. The use of poorly controlled or inadequately specified raw materials may lead to several challenges in dc, such as poor flow ability, inconsistent tablet weight, unsatisfactory tablet strength, lack of content uniformity or segregation and dissolution failure.^[5]

❖ *Advantages*^[5]

1. effective production
2. Better stability of API
3. Faster dissolution
4. Lower microbial contaminations
5. Less wear and tear of punches

❖ *Limitations*^[5]

1. Segregation
2. Variation in functionality
3. Low dilution potential
4. Rework ability
5. Poor compressibility of API
6. Lubricant sensitivity

MATERIAL**Table no. 6.1: List of chemicals and their manufacturers.**

Sr.no.	Material	Manufactures	Category
1	Ketoprofen	SYNGENESIS CHEMSCIENCE Pvt. Ltd. Pune.	NSAID, Analgesic, Antipyretic
2	Crospovidone	Dipa Enterprises, Sambhajinagar.	Superdisintegrant
3	Mannitol SD	Lab Line Stock Centre Mumbai.	bulking agent
4	Sorbitol	Lab Line Stock Centre Mumbai.	Sweetner
5	Magnesium stearate	Dipa Enterprises, Sambhajinagar.	Flow agent
6	Colloidal s	Lab Line Stock Centre Mumbai.	Absorbent
7	MCC	Lab Line Stock Centre Mumbai.	Disintegrant

GLASSWARE'S AND EQUIPMENTS**Table no. 6.2: Glassware & Equipments.**

Sr.No.	Glasswares
1	Beaker
2	Glassrod
3	Measuring Cylinder
4	Volumetric flask
5	funnel
6	Mortar and pestle

COMPATIBILITYSTUDYOF DRUG AND EXCIPIENT**Table No. 6.3: Compatibility Study of Drug and Excipient.**

Sr. no.	Drug+Excipient	Ratio
1	Drug	1
2	Drug + Crospovidone	1:1
3	Drug + Mannitol	1:1
4	Drug + Sorbitol	1:1
5	Drug + Mg Stearate	1:1
6	Drug+ Colloidal S	1:1
7	Drug+ MCC	1:1

EQUIPMENT**Table no.6.4: Equipments.**

Sr.No.	Instruments	Model	Manufacturers
1	Digitalbalance	AUX-220	Shimadzu, Japan
2	Hot air oven	PEW-202/PEW-205	Pathak electrical work, Mumbai
3	UV-visible spectrophotometer	UV-1900i	Shimadzu Analytical(India) PVT.LTD
4	pH meter	EQ-610	Equiptronics Instruments(India) PVT.LTD
5	Tablet compression machine	KM16	Karnavati Engineering Limited, Mhesana, Gujrat

P	Hardness tester	8M	ELECTROLAB(India) PVT.LTD
7	Dissolution apparatus	DS 8000	ELECTROLAB(India) PVT.LTD
8	Disintegration apparatus	Labline,DBK5162/1 ,DBK	Analab scientific INST.PVT.LTD

Experimental work

1. Organoleptic properties

This include recording of colour odorand taste of the drug record of colour is very usefull in establishing appropriate of batches. The preformulation studies include the physicochemical characterization ofthe drug and excipients which are useful in formulation the dosage form.^[3]

2. Melting point

The measurement of melting points is a relatively straightforward procedure that is carried out to determine the purity of a compound or to assist with its identification. A pure compound will melt over a relatively narrow temperature range, impurities both lower and widen the temperature range over which a compound melts.^[7]

• Thiele's Tube Method

A sample drug Ketoprofen is sealed in capillary, attached to a thermometer with a rubber band, immersed in thieles tube Heating is commenced, and the temperature ranges at which the sample melts can then be observed. During heating, the point at which melting is observed and the temperature constant is the melting point of the sample drug Ketoprofen.^[7]

Fig no. 7.1: Melting Point Assembly.

3. UV-Spectrometry

The organic in the when exposed to light in the ultra-violet region of the spectrum, absorbed

light of particular wave length depending on the type of electronic transition associated with absorptions.^[19]

- ***λMax Determination***

The extend to which sample absorb light depends upon the wave length of light. The wavelength at which a substance shows maximum absorbance is called λ_{max} . Sample were subjected to UV spectrophotometric analysis and were scanned for absorption maxima in the range of 200- 400 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer in an appropriate medium.^[19]

4. Standard Calibration Curve

Stock Solution 1

Stock solution of drug (1mg/ml) is prepared by dissolving 100 mg of the drug in 100 sodium hydroxide buffer pH 6.8 in 100 ml volumetric flask(to get 1000mg/ml drug solutions) with vigorous shaking and further sonicated for about 10 minutes.

Stock Solution 2

10 ml of this (stocks solution 1) is diluted to 100 ml with sodium hydroxide buffer pH 6.8 (to get stock solution containing 100mg/ml of drug). The stock solution was filtered.

Dilutions

Take the respective sample (0ml, 1ml, 2ml, 3ml, 4ml) in each test tube. Add sodium hydroxide buffer 6.8 to make total volume of 10 ml to produce (0ppm, 10ppm, 20ppm, 30ppm, 40ppm) respectively.^[12]

5. Determination of solubility

One gram of ketoprofen were taken in beaker and slowly known amount of water were added after complete dissolution of drug the volume required for dissolution of drug was noted. In same way one gram of ketoprofen were dissolved in ethanol.^[18]

Evaluation of tablet

1. Thickness test

The thickness of individual tablets is measured by using vernier caliper which gives the accurate measurement of thickness. It provides information of variation of thickness between tablets Generally the unit for thickness measurement is mm. The limit of the thickness deviation of each tablet is 5%.^[10]

2. *Hardness test*

The hardness of a tablet is associated with the resistance of the solid specimen towards fracturing and attrition. The hardness of tablets can be determined by using Monsanto hardness tester and measured in terms of kg/cm^2 .^[3]

3. *Weight variation test*

The weight variation test was done by weighing 20 tablets individually (Shimadzu digital balance), calculating the average weight and comparing the individual tablet weights to the average. The percentage weight deviation was calculated and then compared with USP specification.^[10]

4. *Disintegration Test (U.S.P.)*

The U.S.P. device to test disintegration consists of 6 glass tubes that are inch long open at the top and 10 mesh screens at the bottom end. During the disintegration test, one tablet is placed in each tube and the basket rack is peniti in a 1- L beaker of either water, simulated gastric fluid or simulated intestinal fluid at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ such that the tablet remainsn 2.5 cm below the surface of liquid on their upward movement and not closer than 2.5 cm from the bottom of the beaker in their downward movement Move the basket containing the tablets up and down through 5-6 cmat a frequency of 28-32cycles per minute.^[12]

5. *Wetting time*

A piece of tissue paper (12cm x10.75cm) folded twice was placed in a Petri dish (Internal Diameter=9cm) containing 10ml of buffer solution simulating saliva pH 6.8 and amaranth. A tablet was placed on the paper and the time taken for complete wetting was noted. Three tablets from each formulation were randomly selected and the average wetting time was recorded.^[10]

6. *Friability*

The pharmacopoeial limit of friability test for a tablet is not more than 1% using tablet friability apparatus, carried out at 25 rpm for 4 min (100 rotations). However, it becomes a great challenge for a formulator to achieve friability within this limit for MDT product keeping hardness at its lowest possible level in order to achieve a minimum possible disintegration time. This test is again not applicable for lyophilized and flash dose tablets, but is always recommended for tablets prepared by direct compression and moulding techniques to ensure that they have enough mechanical strength to withstand the abrasion

during shipping and shelf life^[12]

Formulation^[5]

Table no. 7.1: Formulation of FDT(250mg).

Sr no	Material	F1 (In mg)	F2 (in mg)	F3 (in mg)	use
1	Ketoprofen	50	50	50	API
2	Crospovidone	20	25	15	Superdisintegrant
3	Mannitol SD	80	116	126	Binder/sweetening agent
4	Sorbitol	20	40	44	Binder/diluents/
5	Mg-stearate	2	2	2	lubricant
6	Colloidal S	2	2	2	Adsorbent
7	MCC	11	11	11	binder /diluents
	TOTAL	250	250	250	

• Method Formulation of Fast Dissolving Tablets

Fast dissolving tablets containing selected solid dispersion were prepared by direct compression method using single punch tablet machine to produce convex faced tablets part of them weighing 250mg and others 400mg. 100 tablets were prepared for each batch. The tablet formulations were developed by using Superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium and Crospovidone) in varying concentration (2-10%). All the ingredients shown in Table (1.1) were passed through sieve no.70 and were co-grounded in a glass pestle motor. These blends were evaluated for mass-volume relationship Bulk Density and Tapped Density, Hauser's Ratio, and Compressibility Index and flow properties Angle of Repose. The mixed blended drug excipients were compress using a single punch tablet machine to produce convex faced tablets.^[5]

RESULTS

1. Organoleptic properties

Table no. 8.1: Organoleptic properties.

Sr.NO.	Identification test	Observation
1	Solubility	Ethanol and (DMSO&DMF)
2	Colour	White or Off white
3	Odour	Odourless
4	Nature	Fine to granular powder
5	Taste	Intensely sweet

2. Melting point

Table no. 8.2: Melting point.

Observed Melting Point	Standard Melting Point	Inference
94°C	96.8°C	Complies as per IP

3. Determination of λ_{\max}

The λ_{\max} of pure ketoprofen was found to be 260 nm by using UV visible spectroscopic method solution was scanned over between 400 and 200 nm using UV spectrophotometer (UV-1900i, SHIMADZU Corp., Japan). The absorption maxima (λ_{\max}) was obtained at 260 nm.

Fig no. 8.1: UV Spectrum of Ketoprofen in Standard Solution.

4. Evaluation of ketoprofen FDTs

Table no. 8.3: Parameters & Values.

Sr. No.	Parameter	F1	F2	F3
1.	Thickness(mm)	3.53±0.50	3.97±0.30	3.83±0.55
2.	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	4.3±0.3	4.5±0.1	4.8±0.2
3.	Weight variation(mg)	249.78±2.34	249.68±2.02	239.78±3.07
4.	Friability{ %w/w }	1.26±0.02	1.26±0.01	1.22±0.05
5.	Disintegration Time(sec.)	55.22±0.3	32.33±0.2	56.23±0.4
6.	Wetting time(min.)	2.59±0.3	1.14±0.2	2.58±0.3

Solubility Studies of Ketoprofen

Table no. 8.4: Solubility And Description

Sr.No.	Solvent	Description
1	Water	Insoluble
2	Ethanol	Soluble

Calibration Curve of Ketoprofen

Fig. no. 8.2: Calibration curve of ketoprofen.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY

Ketoprofen is widely used as an analgesic, and being so, the faster the effect, the better the dosage form. Therefore solid preparations of Ketoprofen with superdisintegrants like Crospovidone in different ratios were prepared with a view to increase its effect by decreasing the time required for the drug to be released. Ketoprofen and the excipients were mixed together and submitted to pre- formulation tests. The powders were then compressed into tablets by direct compression method. The prepared batches of tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, disintegration time, wetting time and in- vitro drug release. Formula F2 showed the best disintegration times of 30 seconds and maximum drug release from Formula F2 about 98% in 2 minutes.

CONCLUSION

Ketoprofen, an NSAID, was selected as a model for preparation of fast dissolving tablets by direct compression technique. Fast dissolving tablets were prepared by adding different concentrations of superdisintegrant (crospovidone) and three formulae of ketoprofen FDTs have been prepared, utilizing different excipients. All prepared FDTs were evaluated for weight variation, thickness uniformity, friability, hardness, wetting time, water absorption

time, dispersion time, disintegration time, and dissolution time. The aforementioned results revealed that formula F2 was the best ketoprofen FDT.

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